

The Demystification Of Beethoven's Figure And The Creation Of A New Myth Through Human Attributes (Fan Stilian Noli- "Betoveni Dhe Revolucioni Francez")

Hasan Pristina, Fehmi Agani

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 15, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 17, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Analysis, Beethoven, Intertextuality, Method Of Comparison, Musicology, Mythology, Recontextualization, Retrieval</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5790380</p>	<p><i>Mythology is considered to be one of the main sources of literature. As such, it has become the object of study for many researchers in this field, at all levels of recovery. And such a figure, both real and mythical, is the object of study in this paper, making a detailed analysis of the transitions from the real to the mythological plane that the Albanian author, Fan Stilian Noli, makes to the figure of Beethoven in the book "Beethoven and the French Revolution."</i></p> <p><i>The interweaving of a real figure with the myth enabled the use of the comparison's method to see more closely the human and mythical characteristics that Beethoven had. Meanwhile, the analysis and dissemination of levels of intertextuality allow the study to decompose these elements in more detail.</i></p> <p><i>All these methods are put into function by the purpose of the study, which tends to decompose the passage of this real figure into a mythical domain. The writer's "play" with the figure of Beethoven, first demystifying it from the mythical veil given to it, then mythologizing it in a human context, overthrowing previous deities, giving new attributes, real facts, and mythical attire, and finally, the contextualization and recontextualization of Beethoven's image, brings a new, previously unknown approach to this great figure of musicology.</i></p>

Introduction

This research, which has as its goal the figure of Beethoven, the most important figure in world musicology, belongs to the discipline of literature. As previously said, it is precisely this characteristic that distinguishes the work as unique and inventive, as it presents Beethoven in a new light.

The fact that a globally recognized figure is being addressed from a different perspective has prompted researchers to delve further into the most professional behavior of all these interliterary planes via which Beethoven's figure passes. Because the field into which Beethoven's figure is introduced is not widely known, it has been estimated that the work dialectically deconstructs the author's entire objective. So, starting with the paratextual markers, we'll progress through his undressing from the mythological curtain, providing human traits, and finally deification. Meanwhile, the entire linked theory is devoted to the most accurate interpretation of all literary themes. As such, the study is of great interest because it brings Beethoven's great figure, from a previously unknown dimension.

1. Methodology

The field of literature, especially when combined with mythology, allows for a wide range of methodologies to be used. The strategies that produce the best outcomes in this domain include intertextuality and comparison, with deepening at all levels and sub-levels.

The methodology of the study is defined a priori by the book that will be the subject of this paper. Because mixing mythology with a real character necessitates a deeper investigation and research at all intertextual levels, as well as an examination of the possible indicators that this figure may bear, such as a reading culture or universal cognition.

2. Indicators of paratextuality

According to Nathalie Piegay-Gross "*Para-textuality sends signals to any relationship a text holds with its pre-text (preface, remarks, illustrations, etc.)*" (Piegay-Gross, 2011, p.8), thus helping the inter-textual line to be easier to understand or even to navigate. When discussing the five types of trans-textual relationships, Genette emphasizes the importance of pre-context. "Beethoven and the French Revolution" is built on the criterion of allocating the respective titles to different issues, which Fan Noli treats, grouping them by their character. Pre-textual indicators first preceded the publication of the original book, which was in English, "Beethoven and the

French Revolution," by Bishop Fan S. Noli, Mus. B, Ph.D., International Universities Press, New York, 1947. These undoubtedly serve as preliminary data, informing the reader of the book in question as a first and original publication, with details on the author as well. So Fan Noli had a doctoral dissertation on this book, with which he earned his PhD. The details of the translation into Albanian, as well as proofreading, were done by Nebill Dino and Alqi Krsto, translators, and Mehmet Gjevori, lecturer.

Following these indicators, there is a dedication: "*Remembering my father, Stylian Jorgji Nlit, Kantor of the Albanian Church of the Town Village of Ibrik-Tepe, Eastern Thrace, my first music teacher, F.S.N*" (Stilian Noli, 1988, p. 149). As an external indication, this dedication gives details and information about his father, who was the cantor of the church in his hometown, Ibrik Tepe. In addition, on the following page, still unpublished, is a passage from Ludwig van Beethoven, taken from a letter sent to Braytkoff Hertel on November 2, 1809.

"There is something else! Nothing I can learn immediately! However, since my youth, I have longed to understand the wisdom and good things of the past. It is a sin for an artist if he does not perceive the lack of such a desire as the same guilt and does not try to fill this void"(Stilian Noli, 1988, p.151).

Thus, this somehow will be his motto throughout the journey of "Beethoven and the French Revolution", attempting, with a bloodbath of knowledge and wisdom, proclaimed by Beethoven himself, to reveal the truth.

Following the external data, comes the next section of book titles. It is characteristic that all sections, except the title, also have a detached, statement-like part above the text. Thus, the book begins with the Introduction, which is the first part, preceded by a Meternic quote, "When France gets cold, all Europe sneezes"(Stilian Noli, 1988, p.155).

After that comes the second part, sources, also preceded by a part taken by St. Matthew, XVII, 2. And "*he was transfigured in front of them, with a face like the sun and a garment as white as light*" (Stilian Noli, 1988, p.163).Part Three is Beethoven Man, and the above holds a part of Beethoven's letter sent to Peters on June 5, 1822.

"Ajme!" No matter how brilliant his silence may be, the artist does not enjoy the privilege of celebrating Jupiter's day at Olympus. Unfortunately, the ordinary world rarely inadvertently descends to these pure heavenly heights"(Stilian Noli, 1988, p.179).

The fourth part is Rebel Beethoven, and has this text above: Freiheit uber Alles-Beethoven. (Freedom above all - Beethoven).

It ends with the bibliography, which contains letters, comments, and reviews from various figures, such as George Bernard Shaw, Thomas Man, Jan Sibelius, Ernest Newman, etc., dedicated to the most serious book on the problem of political ideology in Noli's Beethoven.

3. Overthrowing the previous myth, creating the anti-myth

As a historical creator, Noli has been reluctant to deal more with the heroes and bring them down from their high and untouchable pedestals into the midst of the common people, where they will live, rejoice, suffer, conquer and fail with them. In addition, his opinion is inspired by the firm belief that the real man is more interesting than all the legendary heroes put together, for the simple reason that the latter are a product of the hero's imagination.

Therefore, Noli, by overthrowing the previous myth, creates the anti-myth. In myth, we find a three-dimensional scheme: the signified, the signifier, and the sign. However, according to Barthes theories "*it is a special system in the sense that it is built on a sociological string that existed before it: it is a secondary sociological system*" (Barthes, 2016, p. 245).

Considering that Bart, in this case, sees myth as a lecturism, which speaks of discourse-object, Noli's anti-myth will be the new myth of metalecturism and object-discourse. Because it will ignore both the script and the image of this script, it will build the new script image and image itself. Therefore, Noli builds a new system that is an anti-myth or a new personal myth.

As he criticizes glorification at any cost to the hero, he subtracts them from the aristocratic pedestal that they have necessarily put themselves on to give it a human dimension. However, Noli demystifies the myths, for though he sees Beethoven from every possible human lacquer and strips him of the elements that make him divine, he will create a new myth, that of the Beethoven human.

4. The creation of anti-myth as reversal of myth

In addition, the idea of overthrowing the myth of Beethoven's image begins with its origins.

Mensur Raifi refers to this when he says:"*Rishqyrtimi i njemendte i heroit dhe heroizmit, si nje kthim nga vetvetja dhe rivleresim i punëve personale, fillon pikërisht me shqyrtimin e prejardhjes së heroit. Kjo është kritika e parë që i bën Noli legjendës mbi origjinën fisnike dhe aristokrate të domosdoshme të madhështisë së heroit.*"(Raifi, 1979, p. 81). (The real re-examination of the hero and heroism, as a return to itself and a re-evaluation of personal affairs, begins precisely with the examination of the origin of the hero. This is the first criticism Noli makes of the legend about the noble and aristocratic origins necessary for the hero's greatness).

Thus, Noli expresses the view that a man does not necessarily have to be noble and aristocratic. Seeing this idea more as a prejudice and as a pretext to glorify and mitigate the hero, researcher Raifi thinks that Noli, already through arguments, proves that the people's leaders, the great creators, by no means come out of a big door.

This is citation from the text: "*Tani vijnë të Betoveni, si bir i Feudalizmit Mesjetar, që besonte në epërsinë e gjakut aristokrat dhe në urdhrat e medaljet e mbretërve të aristokracisë. Fjala 'Van' përpara emrit të Betovenit nuk është një titull fisnikërie në gjuhën e Flandrës, sikurse është 'Von' në gjuhën gjermane, po Betoveni ua mbushi mendjen miqve të tij aristokratë në Vjenë se ajo kishte po atë kuptim.* (Stilian Noli, 1988, p.245). (Now we come to Beethoven, the son of Medieval Feudalism, who believed in the supremacy of aristocratic blood and the orders and medals of the kings of the aristocracy. The word 'Van' before the name of Beethoven is not a noble title in the Flanders language, as is the word 'Von' in the German language, but Beethoven persuaded his aristocratic friends in Vienna that it had the same meaning).

However, this will not continue for a long time for Beethoven because he will be exposed, "tearing down the tale of his nobility," as Noli claims.

The author writes this: "*Shindleri besnik e pranon me pahir se mjeshtri hiqej si fisnik teksa ishte nga klasa e borgjezisë së vogël. Përralla e fisnikërisë së Betovenit u shemb kur Gjykata aristokrate Landhaus, i kërkoi atij dokumente për të provuar fisnikërinë e tij. Ai s'kishte të tilla dokumente. Për pasojë, çështja e të nipit të tij u hodh në Gjykatën popullore të Vjenës, Betoveni u zemërua shumë përpara këtij çgradimi dhe shkroi me dorën e tij këtë vërejtje në Fletoret e Bisedimeve: "Natyra ime tregon se unë nuk i përkas vegjëlisë"* (Stilian Noli, 1988, p. 252.). (The faithful Schindler admits emphatically that the master was cast as a nobleman while in the petty bourgeoisie class. The tale of Beethoven's nobility collapsed when the aristocratic Landhaus Court asked him for documents to prove his nobility. He had no such documents. As a result, his nephew's case was brought before the People's Court of Vienna. Beethoven became angry long before this degradation, and wrote with his own hand in the Notebooks: "My nature shows that I do not belong to childhood."

Thus, Noli plays with form and concept, which in this case is the marker of myth. So the marker, Beethoven, has a fortune and requires a read. And, being part of a story, this myth has a value in itself, which implies a past, a memory, a sequence of facts, ideas, etc., but by passing on a mythical marker, becoming a form, the meaning is stripped away from its own context. And this game between meaning and form defines myth. And yet, this form gives Noli a new meaning. You strip it off, "dressing" it again.

And, starting from the legend that the hero is always divine or at least of aristocratic descent, Nietzsche and Ibsen, though descended from the petty bourgeoisie, have tried at all costs and with great desire to prove and persuade the masses of noble descent. . The big impact must have been from some legends, as Noli mention "*qytetërimi modern është pjellë e klasave të larta*", dhe se "*tipi më i lartë i heroit është luftëtari, gjahtori i kokave dhe kanibali*" (Stilian Noli, 1988, p. 254). (modern civilization is the offspring of the upper classes, and that "the highest type of hero is the warrior, the head hunter, and the cannibal), but the author calls them absurdities.

Thus, Noli plays with form and concept, which in this case is the marker of myth. So the marker, Beethoven, has a fortune and requires a read. And being part of a story, as Roland Barthes says, this "*myth has a value of its own, which implies a past, a memory, a sequence of facts, ideas, etc., but passing on a mythical marker, becoming a form, the meaning is stripped away. from its own context*" (Barthes, 2016, p. 253). And, this game between meaning and form defines myth. And yet, this form gives Noli a new meaning. Strip it down, 'dressing' it again

5. The new myth, humanized figure of Beethoven

Fan.S.Noli, after stripping away the first myth, the myth of the idol Beethoven, the divine aristocrat, tends to create a new myth. Therefore, from the anti-myth we come to the myth, now to the new myth. It seems to Noli that this reckless glorification of the hero, which has nothing to do with the truth, is prevented. Mensur Raifi claims "*With the power of arguments, he causes the hero to descend from legendary heights on earth. He cuts off the wings of idolatry and gives it real dimensions*". (Raifi, 1979, p.83).

At the heart of the myth, the concept will embrace a whole new story, as Noli will, through the new concept, give a different story to the new Beethoven myth. And moving from meaning to form, the image loses knowledge, because the knowledge contained in the mythical concept is a blurry knowledge. The concept is thus filled with new knowledge.

Moreover, the new myth first begins with its appearance. Demystifying the legend of the beautiful appearance of the heroes, Noli gives a new look to the hero, namely, Beethoven, which is far removed from the statues, or the imagination of Beethoven's idolaters.

"*Betoveni i vërtetë është i shëmtuar si majmun. I pazhvilluar si kërcu, me një fytyrë të zeshkët e vrazëlije, me një hundë të mprehtë e fllashkë, me sy të vegjël e të dobët, shëmbë katarosh, flokë të zeza dhe kreshtë, duar të shkurtra e gishta të trashë, - ai dukej si ari i palëpirë, si totem krye-gorgonë, si gogol fantastik, ose mishërim i njeriut origjinal të shpellave*" (Stilian Noli, 1988, p.82), this is how the author describes Beethoven. (Real Beethoven is ugly like a monkey. Underdeveloped like a cartilage, with a murderous brunette face, with a sharp,

bubbly nose, small, slender eyes, catharsis, black hair and crest, short hands and thick fingers, he looked like raw gold, like top-gorgon totem, fantastic bugbear, or incarnation of the original caveman.

Therefore, the myth of the hero Beethoven, with the appearance of a nobleman, collapses to give way to a new myth, which gives it ugly traits. In addition, Noli will not leave out Beethoven's bodily appearance, at this level of feature reversal. Claiming that he was a simple man above all, and part of a multitude of ugly, ugly, sicknesses, Noli once again attempts to bring humanity to Beethoven in the eyes of humankind.

“Legjenda tjetër që të dërmon është që të gjithë heronjtë, fizikisht, janë yrenkë tipikë herkulianë. Sipas rregullit, nuk janë ashtu. Për shembull, Betoveni ishte një gërmadhë trupore, vetëm e vetëm një ulog. Ai na rrëfen vetë se ka qenë gjithë jetën shëndetligë. Në vogëli i ka pasë rënë lija, që ndikoi edhe në sytë e tij e ia prishi edhe fytyrën. Në letrat e tij ai ankohet vazhdimisht për veshët e dobët, për sytë e mahisur, për astmën, cermën e këmbëve, përdhesin, të verdhët, oreksuon, të prerët e barkut dhe dhembjën e zorrëve. Në vjetët e tij të fundit u paralizua nga shurdhësia dhe diarreja kronike. Më në fund vdiq prej cirozës së mëlçive”. (Stilian Noli, 1988, p. 89). (“The other legend that crushes you is that all the heroes, physically, are typical Hercules. As a rule, they are not. Beethoven, for example, was a carnal ruin, just an ulog. He confesses to himself that he has been healthy all his life. At the young age he had varicella, which affected both his eyes and his face. In his letters he constantly complains about weak ears, lacerated eyes, asthma, rash, gout, jaundice, appetite, abdominal cuts and intestinal aches. In his final years he was paralyzed by deafness and chronic diarrhea. He eventually died of cirrhosis of the liver.”)

However, in the tendency to mythologize, Noli will point out precisely the fact that Beethoven had many bodily ailments and insecurities, to see as his heroism his attempt to defeat them. Moreover, the combination of all those masterpieces with this entire bodily burden on his shoulder makes Beethoven a myth.

Researcher Raifi thinks it is important to see to what extent Noli has succeeded in humanizing the legendary and mythical figure of Beethoven and to what extent he has created a new myth. Today, all over the world, myth is a second reality for man.

Each mythologist, however lucid he is, demystifies one myth and automatically creates another.

As Bart states in "Mythologies", the mythologist has a mythology of his own. Therefore, even Noli, faced with legends and facts, realistically ugly Beethoven, giving human dimensions, also wears the hero's garment. Because, he was actually destined to be a hero.

Noli's Betoven cannot be considered as a hero like Hercules, but his works resemble with those of Hercules. He is not, indeed, sober before the blessed wine, nor a virgin before the Viennese Omphalies, but is in his own way, like Brutus, the hero-killer-of-the-Titans. But Noli recognizes that nothing can harm the gods, consequently nothing can harm the god Beethoven.

Therefore, the overthrown myth of Beethoven's aristocrat is brought back into play as a humanized myth.

6. Conclusion

Literature and its connection with real-life people have always provided scholars with the essential room to apply study from various planes and dimensions of literary theory.

The research was designed to create Beethoven's new image, shattering his previous divine image and mythologizing him through human characteristics. This fact is a novelty in and of itself, and it surely provides a fresh source of riches for the study of this topic in general, and especially of this famous world figure in particular. However, it is intended in a future study that the picture presented to Beethoven by author Fan Noli act as a near approximation to truth, as history also knows, thus seeking to unite the fields of literature and history, and in which case this study would be even more comprehensive.

References

- Apolloni, Ag, *“Parabola postmoderne”*, OM, Prishtinë, 2010.
 Barthes, Roland, *Mitologjitë, Shtëpia e librit*, Prishtinë, 2016.
 Chevrel, Yeves, *“Letërsi e krahasuar”*, Tiranë, Albin, 2002
 Frenz, Hors, editor, Newton P. Stallknecht editor, *“Comparative Literature: Method and Perspective”*, “Southern Illinois University Press”, Carbondale, IL.
 Gashi, Osman, *“Letërsia dhe miti”*, OM, Prishtinë, 2014.
 Lévi-Strauss, Claude, *Myth and Meaning*, Taylor & Francis e-Library, London, 2005
 Meletinsky, Yelezar, *The Poetics of Myth*, Routledge, New York, 2000.
 Piegay-Gross, Nathalie, *“Poetika e intertekstualitetit”*, Parnas, Prishtinë, 2011.
 Raifi, Mensur, *Fan S.Noli dhe Migjeni*, Rilindja, Prishtinë, 1979.
 Raifi, Mensur, *Lasgushi, Noli dhe Migjeni*, Rilindja, Prishtinë, 1986
 Rrahmani, Kujtim, *Intertekstualiteti dhe Oraliteti*, AIKD, Prishtinë, 2002.
 Shehri, Dhurata, *Statusi i kritikës*, Albas, Tiranë, 2013.
 Stilian Noli, Fan, *Vepra 5*, Rilindja, Prishtinë, 1988.

Stilian Noli, Fan*Vepra 1*, Rilindja, Prishtinë, 1988.

Stilian Noli, Fan, *Betoveni dhe Revolucioni francez*, Rilindja, Prishtinë, 1968.

Tirta, Mark, *Mitologjia ndër shqiptarë*, Akademia e Shkencave, Tiranë, 2004.

Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven, "*Comparative Literature: Theory, Method, Application*", Amsterdam, Rodopi, 1998.

Author Information

Hasan Pristina

PhD (cand.) at University of Pristina, Kosovo

Fehmi AganiTeaching Assistant at University of Gjakova, Kosovo
